

PROJECT INDEXMED: ORIGINAL SOLUTIONS TO MANAGE THE HETEROGENEITY OF MARINE ECOLOGY DATA IN THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA

Romain David¹, Jean-Pierre Feral¹, Anne-Sophie Archambeau², Nicolas Bailly³, Cyrille Blanpain⁴, Aurélie Delavaud, Alrick Dias¹, Julien Lecubin⁴, Isabelle Mougnot, Geneviève Romier⁵, Christian Surace⁶, Thierry Taton¹ and the IndexMed community

¹IMBE, CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, France

²GBIF, France

³HCMR and MedOBIS, Greece

⁴SIP OSU Pytheas, CNRS, France

⁵Ecoscope, FRB, France

⁶Espace-Dev, Montpellier Université, France

⁷IdGC, CNRS, France Grilles

⁸LAM, CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, France

Concerning studies about biodiversity and socio-ecological systems (SES), the data production in the coastal and marine area is expensive and still has a low level of automation. Long time series and/or large spatial areas studies are difficult to conduct, and when it is necessary to involve several observers, the robustness and reproducibility of the observation is more difficult to obtain.

In a production framework of multi-source data, equivalence of observation systems and their inter-calibration become crucial. Multi-disciplinary or trans-disciplinary integrative approaches become necessary in the study of systems where output of each discipline is discontinuous, imprecise and poorly distributed. Yet all variables (biotic, abiotic, anthropogenic and natural pressures, felt and rendered services, societal image...) of these systems interact over time and at each spatial scale.

A better overall understanding of the balance of SES and their influence on biodiversity will be permitted by constructing and testing co-interpretation methods of analyses of these heterogeneous data. Data mining methods must be able to bring new perspectives to the disciplinary researches that finally examine interrelated objects (environmental chemistry, genomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, population ecology / landscape, socio-ecological systems).

The IndexMed consortium aims to identify and overcomes the scientific barriers related to data quality and heterogeneity. The use of graph-based model allows us to consider them, despite their differences, at a similar level, and improves decision support using emerging data mining methods (collaborative clustering, machine learning, mining graphs, knowledge representation, etc).

Keywords: interdisciplinarity, data qualification, standards, data dictionary, thesaurus, ontologies, inter-calibration, decentralized information system, integrated coastal management